

Research Paper

Administrative bottlenecks hindering efficiency in the practice of public administration

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ABSTRACT

The study assessed administrative bottlenecks that affects efficiency in the practice or workings of individuals or civil servants in public administration. Administrative bottlenecks are common causes that hinder effective discharge of duties in an establishment or organization, as it creates opportunities for frustration, decrease in productivity, political influence and unnecessary waste of time and resources in an establishment. Administrative bottlenecks arise from bureaucracy in an establishment. This culminates into excessive red-tape, slow decision-making processes and inadequate flow of communication. Administrative bottlenecks affect the practice of public administration and also lead to poor service delivery, poor implementation of policies and low staff morale, thereby hindering efficiency, transparency and responsiveness. Accordingly, the objectives of the study were to deal with the issues of ineffective communication, low productivity, redundancy, indiscipline in work places and exploitation etc. Addressing these challenges the study adopted the qualitative research method for data generation. It based its theoretical framework on the theory of constraints (TOC), and recommended that processes should be put in place to eliminate redundancy and enhance efficiency and translate political decisions into actionable policies for effective service delivery.

1 | INTRODUCTION

Administrative bottlenecks refer to a situation where the workers' job is impeded by a negative management system. This sought of system creates room for delays and inefficient procedures of managing activities. According to Gutterman (2023) he posits that "serious consideration of managerial roles and activities is often traced back to the work of Henri Fayol, who was one of the first to focus on the specific functions and roles of managers and famously observed in his writings in the early 20th century that *managers had five principles roles: planning, organizing, commanding, coordinating and controlling*". Within the context of organizations, these five principles exist and they play significant roles in the management of public administration. As they also play crucial roles in effective leadership and operational efficiency. As Stallings and Ferris have noted, the field of public administration possesses a wealth of research questions and methodological tools, but it has yet to find an effective way to bridge the gap between the two. (Kraemer & Perry, 1989). The presence of administrative bottlenecks in an organization negates the establishment's objectives to determining the best course of action. Recourses in this regard shall not be optimally utilized, and communication becomes ineffective and distorted. In any organization, uninterrupted communication flow should be *downward* from management to the workforce (this can take the form of operating instructions), *upwards*, from the workforce to management, a type of feedback to management on any instruction given or reaction from workforce to management on areas of policies, instructions or decisions. This could be the reason why Oaikhena (2023) observed that "the quality of employee behavior or performance will also be influenced by the degree of human resource development policy in the organization". When policies are not properly implemented, public managers are said to have failed.

Furthermore, administrative bottlenecks are described as processes where frustration and inefficiency is prevalent, resulting in low productivity in the value of work, as it also creates confusion and inefficient capacity. As capacity is hindered, the environment, organization and governmental agencies are impacted negatively, thus influencing or affecting productivity. The conduct of an organization or administrative system is centered around its management, and employee or civil servants, as the case may be, hence it is measured against acceptable ethical standards by the customer, supplier, and members of the society, in the promotion of administrative decisions. The values involved in the promotion of administrative decisions are seldom final values in psychological or philosophical sense since most objectives and activities derive their value from the means and relationships which connect them with objectives or activities that are valued in themselves. The study opined that the practice of public administration is a stimulus for the creation of society awareness of efficiently and developing the environment around us, through efficient management system. Whether we like it or not efficiency

develop individuals' knowledge, emotion and morality, as well as, practical competence. Bottlenecks that hinder competence is a distraction from the norm and behaviour pattern in any administrative system. This influence has direct or indirect consequences for society at large. This is particularly true because, through its impact on civil servants or individuals, negative assumption is bound to occur, leading to societal change. Since bottlenecks affect society and individuals, the attitude, values and spontaneous reactions began to manifest towards productivity, as it takes its tools on economic and social environment of the state. Without doubt, administrative bottlenecks inevitably exert influence upon the generality of individuals working in an establishment or organization. Indeed, such influence may be strongest amongst colleagues, relatives, friends and associates, as there is no doubt that this may extend to the larger community and environment as well. Authorities sometimes believe that individuals are passive followers of instructions from institutions or agencies of government, some are even conditioned to adjust to the requirements of the labour market no matter what. The presence of administrative bottlenecks in some establishment creates room for sheepishness amongst individuals working in the system, as it also affects the social environment, such as increase in the number of office workers, specialist, and the level of unemployment. This could be the reason why Savani and Bhargava (2018) observed that "organizations can focus its constrained assets on the primary issues of bottleneck operations to adequately explain the irregularity between singular offices and general objects of the organization".

However, the study most often and without conscious intentions, inclined that administrative bottlenecks may present new opportunities or possibilities of thought and action; new standards, and indeed, new style of leadership, in most establishment. Thus, in the long run, these influence ultimately may results in change in administrative practices, government public policy, societal practices with consequences for state and national economy. Naturally, it is a truism to say that the extent of administrative bottlenecks in the practice of public administration largely results from the value, motive, attitude and competences of the individuals. In view of these, the objectives of this study were to ascertain the level of effect caused by administrative bottlenecks in the practice of public administration, towards effective communication, low productivity, redundancy and exploitation of individuals in the establishment. In contrast, for public administration to be effective and addresses societal and organizational needs, bottlenecks should be mitigated.

2 | PERCEIVED PROBLEMS OF ADMINISTRATIVE BOTTLENECKS

Administrative bottlenecks in the practice of public administration have resulted in uncompleted or poor-quality of public projects and policy

implementation in most organizations. It had caused significant financial losses in some instances and delays in task execution, inefficient use of talent, and also prevent organizations from achieving their set-out goals. According to Bestman (2018), she argued that "... bottleneck is one process in a chain of processes, such that its limited capacity reduces the capacity of the whole chain". Conversely, public administration is hindered by administrative bottlenecks that creates a culture of uncertainty and abuse of human activities. Workers are thus influenced and strongly inclined to believe that they are on a deceptive lane. This could be the reason why Savani and Bhargava (2018) suggested that "globalized transparent systems have cut cost for which systems require a flow of information and adequate control over materials". Hence the practice of administrative duties and cultures which is tied to efficiency, is no longer encouraged to build social values, norms, and morals of civil servants in the society.

Social values, which is the basic benefits that holds the society together, is expected to serve the society or administrative environment. The presence of administrative bottlenecks in an organization has hampered the growth of organizations in a faster rate, affecting the economy in general. In fact, unless the organization, its people and its management have an objective, a corporate identity, a philosophy of what they are in business for and a plan to achieve these objectives, there can be no unified direction that management can use to relate its day-to-day decisions. Management of organizations are mostly concerned with maximum attainment of organizational objectives in diverse ways. This could be the reason why Savani and Bhargava again said that "bottlenecks attract improper returns on the capital applied". It then connotes that any administrative environment that is hampered by inefficiency and under-performance is dictated by individuals' inability to achieve set out objectives, this can be ascribed to attitude towards the prevailing situation in the organization. An organization is in business to achieve certain goals and objectives, this can only be done through the efforts of individuals in the organization. These individual's efforts can only be positively influenced by their need directed behaviour. If the goals of organizations are to motivate people and develop team work, administrative bottlenecks should be minimized if not totally eradicated. According to Sharma, 2007, he argued that "in the realm of public administration, the efficient and effective delivery of services to the citizenry is of paramount importance. However, the practice of public administration is often plagued by administrative bottlenecks, which impede the smooth functioning of government agencies and hinder the realization of their objectives".

A large number of people are afraid of the unknown, created by administrative bottleneck in the practice of public administration. If for instance a goal is set and plans are made against such goals, because it is very possible to measure the success or failure of such a venture, that is enough to frighten some individual workers. People will perform, inefficiently and irresponsibly without prejudice, due to the existence of administrative bottlenecks. This could also be the reason why Boogaard (2022) advised that 'organizations can achieve their goals by identifying and leveraging a system's constraints'.

3 | SOME PERCEIVED AREAS ADMINISTRATIVE BOTTLENECKS COULD OCCUR IN AN ORGANIZATION

- When a leader does not take into consideration the change dynamics of the environment, it could lead to administrative bottlenecks;
- When the right skills are not possessed by employees, as there is standard procedure in place to train and retrain them, bottlenecks are bound;
- When there is no effective communication in the organization;
- The absence of regular meetings that aid the provision of results, success and challenges by individuals or groups, administrative bottlenecks are bound to occur.

It's frustrating, without a doubt, as these becomes constraints in an organization. Keeping in mind that organizations are systems of connected departments and individuals with multiple dependencies. The actions of departments may create ripple effects for other groups. Rather than addressing one-off or short-term conflicts amongst different teams, the theory of constraints as applied by this study, requires that one should step back, identify a single leverage point, and fix it to improve the entire system (Boogaard, 2022). One of the key factors contributing to administrative bottlenecks is the lack of a clear and cohesive strategy for linking important research questions with the appropriate methodologies to address them (Kraemer & Perry, 1989). Accordingly, there is need for a friendly and a more robust cooperation between management and workers in the environment to discourage chaotic individualism and encourage cooperation in job environment, this is to emphasize knowledge and professionalism among workers. The study is also very significant in the sense that for organizations to succeed administrative bottlenecks should be avoided as it stops

subsequent tasks from moving forward, and also have significant impact on productivity, increasing time and financial expenses.

4 | GOAL SETTINGS DEVOID OF CONFLICT CULMINATES IN PRODUCTIVITY

Goal settings devoid of administrative bottlenecks culminates in productivity because it is centered on oriented planning that is flexible for easy adaptability. In view if this the manager must also ask the question "where do we want to go" and how do we achieve set goals devoid of administrative bottlenecks?". According to Offiong (1997), effective leadership and management of private and public organization is an indispensable factor in the growth of organizations. It is imperative to state that managers should understand the effect of administrative bottlenecks in organizations. When goals are set, clarity of purpose is achieved which enhances growth leading to higher satisfaction, productivity and opportunities, devoid of conflict, rancor and misunderstanding. According to Oaikhena (2022), he rightly observed that "when an individual is treated equally and given equal opportunity to express himself, he is able to effectively utilize the talent and resources to improve the living standard of himself and those around". These differences occur when people are unable to tolerate each other, as they become angry and frustrated".

Conflict is the appearance of differences in opinion and interest. As such conflict is neither good nor bad, but provides opportunity for good or bad results. Using it constructively will make it good. Bottlenecks created by managers could easily lead to conflict in an organization. This could be reason why Tonwe (2004) referenced Follet Parker that, "there are three ways of resolving or dealings with organizational conflict, these are; *through domination, compromise, and integration*. On domination, he opined that, this is the easiest way to resolving conflict, but the long run consequences may be disastrous. On the issue of compromise, he said that each side involve in the conflict gives up a part of what it wants in order to reach a settlement. While on integration he wrote that, integration as a method of dealing with conflict, has some advantages over the compromise method, as compromise does not create something new, but only deals with the existing conflict, whereas integration creates something new that leads to invention and emergence of new values". Meanwhile Adenugba & Folorunsho (2012), opined that "the authority structure promotes the abuse of power since at the top, few control the 'down many' establishing a system ruled by 'gods' in the workplace". In view of these, interactions become inevitable and necessary. Interaction requires higher intelligence, keeping perception and a brilliant inventiveness, which are not easy to come by among administrators. This is often due to limitations, as a result of the role they play which emphasize technical tasks and operational responsibilities over direct engagement with the populace. According to Imhabekhai, (2004), posits that "...the contribution of work to the attainment of organizational objectives, management needs to explore the most appropriate manner to make the people they engaged to work to perform their duties creditably". Bottlenecks become obstacles that life of many people becomes patterned in such a way that, they like to demonstrate others. In view of this, problems are theorized when they ought to be taken as proposed activities or practical issues needing quick solution. Language used to buttress an issue thus becomes an obstacle as its creates antagonism and perpetuate conflict in an organization.

From the foregoing, it is evident that administrative bottlenecks create complicated process. Such that some workers particularly the skilled ones, have knowledge and pride in their work, which makes them resent others telling them how to do their work or even what to do in details. Bestman, (2018) opined that "knowledge and expertise is constrained in many different ways such as spiral, social process from were information, interaction, collaborative activities, experience are learnt". Giving orders, especially detailed ones remove responsibility from the person to whom the order is given. Responsibility should be spread as wide as possible and as low as possible. An order devoid of bottlenecks is a response to the law of situation, which take into account the evolving situation and managements part in making it to accomplish set goals. The reality is that, orders hampered by effective communication arise from the work situation itself, and subordinates may contribute to this situation through attitude maneuvers.

5 | REVIEW OF RELEVANT LITERATURES

A study conducted by Mihika Savani, and Akhil Bhargava (2018), on effect of eliminating bottlenecks in operations on organizational performance revealed the impact of bottlenecks in production on organizational performance. The study suggests that identifying and eliminating bottlenecks can improve efficiency and effectiveness. Qntrl (2024) published an article titled bottlenecks examples and solutions. This article discussed common causes of bottlenecks, such as limited resources, inefficient workflows, lack of training, technical issues, overloaded teams, and poor communication. It suggests strategies like process mapping and employee feedback to identify bottlenecks.

Another article by Qflow (2024), published an article titled “bottlenecks in business processes: how to identify and solve them”. The study revealed that bottlenecks lead to tasks accumulation, hindering production. The study identified causes like increased demand, lack of automation, design flaws, and sub-optimal management as hindrance to organizational efficiency. In another vein, Inakefe, Basse, and Inna, (2021) researched on “administrative problem handling in Nigeria’s public sector”. This study highlighted challenges faced by public administrators in Nigeria, including political interference, corruption, inadequate funding, and favoritism. The study suggests the creation of an independent oversight body and enhancing parliamentary oversight to address these issues. Another study was conducted by Okotoni (2001) on problems and prospects of Nigerian bureaucracy. This paper discusses the challenges faced by the Nigerian bureaucracy, including colonial legacy, military rule, and bureaucratic bottlenecks like red tape. It emphasized the need for reforms to improve bureaucratic efficiency.

5.1 | Eight steps towards eliminating administrative bottlenecks in an organization

Source: Authors diagram (2025)

From the above itemized eight steps towards solving administrative bottlenecks in an organisations, it clearly stated that identifying work flow and mapping out strategies towards organizational objectives is a key factor. Work plans must be identified and mapped out for every administrative role. This strengthens the human parts of an organization in order to facilitate its working and making better managerial control. The importance of time as well as cost is taken into consideration. On the area of collecting and analyzing data; this step is employed to gather data/information from different sources to enable decision making easy or the ability to predict trends. It is essential for business or organisations to decide accurately and employ strategy towards effective planning. Prioritizing bottlenecks represents a critical point of congestion in workflows, and production system to avoid the hindrance of overall process of production. The need to address and optimize these constraints is necessary to improve efficiency and productivity. While the optimize process as a step, depicts streamlining workflows by eliminating redundancy. As a result, process optimization which is a systemic approach that aids the improvement of workflows operations in an organization, enhance efficiency, achieve better outcomes and reduce costs. The conduct of root cause analysis could help to identify underlying factors contributing to administrative bottlenecks and proffer lasting solutions. Furthermore, the step on investing in resources and training addresses capacity issues by upgrading the skills and knowledge of employees, leading to more efficient and effective job performance. This results in higher quality output and increase in production. Thus followed by implementation of agile practices to adequately train and support employees in other to ensure everyone understand their roles and responsibilities, emphasize flexibility, collaboration, and continuous improvement of communication in workflow. While the final step is to monitoring and adjustment - this represents regularly reviews in workflow and performance metrics to ensure bottlenecks do not reoccur. This step is a crucial component in both performance management and agile practice to avoid administrative bottlenecks.

6 | COMMUNICATION HAMPERED BY ADMINISTRATIVE BOTTLENECKS

Communication with unclear message or lack of response can significantly impede productivity in an organization. When there is no feedback or response from subordinates, bottlenecks automatically occur, as administration is hampered. The hampering of administrative duties could lead to non-improvement of organizational performance, inefficiency and employer turnover in some instances and mistrust. This could be the reason why Oaikhena, (2023) emphasized that “factors such as polarization, ineffective communication, and perceived lack of transparency can contribute to mistrust”. Fostering an open down policy encourages dialogue between employees and employers. The style adopted in the process of carrying out instruction in leadership leads to positive outcome (Oaikhena, 2011). Thus, dealing with administrative bottlenecks in an organization presupposes that every employee and employer, play major roles to avoid conflict and distortion of information by communicating effectively with the establishment. Employees that are engaged actively through dialogue and feedback mechanism easily build trust through collaboration that improve the working environment. In this regard, misunderstanding, suspicion and the fear that their voices will not be heard are minimized. This study noted that, to effectively engage employees through communication, there is need to encourage feedback, by fostering open dialogue, listening to opinions and maintaining consistency in information shearing. The purpose of sharing information rapidly enhances social communication through the fostering of internal relationship and breaking down barriers in an organization. Thus, opportunities are provided for employees to contribute meaningfully to the development and growth of the establishment. It is necessary to communicate with the employees and expect feedbacks. Ideas and strategies such as these do not create room for administrative bottlenecks but celebrate achievements amongst workers, promotes values and proper engagement.

Administrative bottlenecks distort the primary rationale for the existence of business organizations as effective communication is not attained for certain corporate goals, which could have been achieved through the concerted efforts of groups of people. Hence, no matter its corporate goals, organizations are characterized by their objectives and directed behaviours. These objectives can be more effectively and efficiently achieved (only) through the concerted action (efforts) of all individuals in the organization. When good human relations exist, it will be easy to organize and receive the cooperation of the workers for productive purposes. Good industrial relations and understanding and trust through dialogue are therefore necessary to promote industrial harmony. Conversely, strenuous efforts are made to ensure that values of personnel management, industrial harmony and good individual relations, do not face administrative bottlenecks. It should provide for job security, growth of the employee and a means of encouraging the employee to produce at his/her best under suitable working conditions. Consequently, effective communication must cover the period from when there is a head-hunt for the job to the life of the employee after he/she would have retired from the service of the employer. According to Menshikova, Pruel, Rubtcova and Varlamova, (2020), they rightly observed that “all planning documents indicate the need for measures to optimize the number of managerial personnel; to improve the quality and competence of employees; to establish monitoring of the effectiveness of the public administration system; and to develop an “Electronic parliament and Justice.” To avoid the hampering of communication caused by administrative bottlenecks in the discharge of duties, personnel must receive adequate training and development, human relations, leadership and motivation technicalities, discipline, flow of information, relations with labour unions within, and including the locality where the company is situated.

Since industrial relations is practiced by human beings of diverse natures, standards and goals, management representative should show a lot of good human relations to be able to accommodate the union officials no matter how difficult they may prove. The relationship between the two ranges from mutual antagonism to that of mutual accommodation. The ultimate being mutual accommodation, management should endeavour to encourage the union officials by not resisting their pressures at all times and by having constant dialogue with them until their aim is achieved. Therefore, the establishment of free flow of information between the employees and employer is vital as workers will be well informed on matters which concern them and their views must be sought on existing practices and proposed changes thereon as may affect them. According to Monteiro (2020), he observed that “at the level of civil society in recent years, management by results has been the prescription recommended by business sectors with influences on state and municipal government”. Organizations are vital instruments in any society, and their accomplishments in industry, education, religion and even health care have precipitously raised the standard of living. One can even add that organizations separately possess vast political, economic and social powers to deal effectively with information and communication that could undermine administrative bottlenecks. The

reduction of administrative bottlenecks in organizations becomes sacrosanct through effective communication.

7 | STRENGTHENING ADMINISTRATIVE BOTTLENECKS THROUGH AUTOMATION

The utilization of technology to monitor performance through automation cannot be overemphasized. The management of administrative bottlenecks is seen as a critical opportunity to improve the productivity of the employee. Automation represents the utilization of technology that enhances job performance in an organization. Productivity and effective communication are achieved as the employee is not deficient and his job is made easy. Employee requires dividends from their investments and hopes to reinvest their profits in order to make more money. The desired result can only be achieved through the employment of a combination of resources which include the deployment of technology (machine) that are put in good use by the employer. It thus, require qualified and experienced persons into positions best suited by their qualifications and experience so that they can derive the best satisfaction for the attainment of the establishments' objectives. This permits a specialist in a given set of activities (e.g Accounting, Engineering, Personnel, etc) to enforce the directives within a limited and clearly defined scope of authority. According to Adenuga and Folorunsho, (2012), they posit that "the structure of organizations compels individuals to abide by the associated norms of the group if they must continue to be part of the group; and their behaviour are thus regulated by them, in spite of the norms which motivated individuals before they joined the group". At times, management can go far in its support of staff, so that the distinction between staff is dissolved. Staff has direct responsibility for the accomplishment of the organization's basic goals as technology and staff managers accomplish all set out organizational goals.

Automation also aids in corporate planning in an organization. The determination of future manpower requirement is a difficult job because it is based on assumption, some of which may not come true due to unforeseen circumstances. This aspect of the job is forward looking and is expected to include a specification of the types and number of skills the enterprise would need to achieve its set objectives (expressed in profit, growth, share of the market, service to be rendered etc), managerial, professional, administrative, technical, supervisory, operatives, clerical and others. In contrast however, Plomp (2019), observed that "bottlenecks in dynamic systems are not stable as they can shift due to machine downtime such as faults or preventive maintenance". Thus, expert training is required to effect quantitative and qualitative improvements in workers performance. Automation brings about a forecast, using the current manpower possession as a base, and projecting it into the future to meet the anticipated workload and formulation of plans for recruiting, placing, developing, keeping and properly utilizing the recruited labour force. This recruited labour force strengthens the movement of the business of the enterprise into more favourable climate with the aid of technology. It is pertinent to note that whatever strategy is deployed it will affect the human resources of the organization either to expand, shrink, train or retrain, redeploy or to declare redundancy. Rukayat (2023), rightly observed that "...bureaucracy promotes administrative bottlenecks in the civil service as she opined that "the people must be accessible and confident to set goals and be involved in their realization". Consequently, the importance of the relationship between administrative bottlenecks and automation is to achieve manpower planning that meets organizational objectives and increase efficiency. These also aid the fostering of responsive and efficient working environment, which on the other hand compliments significantly administrative bottlenecks.

8 | THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The theoretical framework for this study was drawn from the theory of constraints (TOC). This theory was propounded by Eliyahu Goldratt in 1984. Since then, the theory has continued to evolve and develop within the world of management practices (www.leanproductoin.com). Bestman (2018) rightly observed that "from management perspective, bottleneck is unnecessary delay caused by observation of formal hierarchy of power in the exercise of routine functions in an organization". In view of these therefore, the theory of constraints takes a scientific approach to improvement. It hypothesizes that every complex system, including manufacturing processes, consists of multiple linked activities, one of which acts as a constraint upon the entire system (the weakest link). This theory recognizes that there are bottlenecks which constrains or limit a worker's performance in an organization. When the worker is not given adequate and timely information about the business objectives and the corporate plans and proper effective planning of an organization, it will hamper the arrangements and projection of the organization. The worker will have no adequate knowledge of the labour environment, and run into problems administratively. More so, constraints that lead to administrative problem could lead to changes not envisaged by the staff, a situation whereby production system fails due to the lack of proper information which could easily make the job more difficult.

This thus creates an ineffective utilization of resources and manpower. There is no doubt that efficient resource and management plans in an organization involves strategies capable of meeting business objectives. As a result, work plan development creates flexible opportunities that aids training, staff retention, recruitment and skill development devoid of constraints.

Constrains creates room for labour turnover which is inimical to the goals and objectives of the organization. Consequently, employers should try to keep their labour force intact by providing adequate information and good condition of services with the required climate for work. The theory of constraints further underscores that there usually would be no improved task efficiency and human satisfaction that ought to have built into peoples' job, greater scope for personal achievement, recognition, more challenges, more opportunities for individual advancement and growth. Accordingly, employee could face inconsistency in discharging their duties, as such inconsistency leads to dissonance behavior, low productivity, and redundancy.

9 | SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The practice of public administration has to do with implementation of governmental policies and programs that prepares civil servants to meet up with effective management of governmental affairs and operations. Administrative bottlenecks become a hindrance to successful service delivery and decentralization (shifting responsibilities). The study revealed clearly that administrative bottlenecks lead to depersonalization as the worker becomes a mere cog in the system and the relations between the worker and management becomes remote. It creates room for obstacles within the organization's administrative processes thereby hindering efficiency and productivity. Decision making processes are slowed down, causing delays in projects timelines and overall task completion, this leads to increase in operation cost, which can affect financial performance in cases of set deadlines. The tendency for organization to grow rapidly can be affected by administrative bottlenecks as it leads to lack of participation, and decrease in output. The study also established that it is the employer's responsibility to determine what the objectives of the organization should be and what the goals in each area of objectives should be. Consequently, the aspect of the employer's responsibility involves hard work and innovative thinking, since it is future oriented. Administrative bottlenecks as discussed in the study distorts organizational objectives, plans, policies, rules and regulations and procedures, as it hampers the workers ability to perform optimally. Accordingly, workers derive from management perspectives, the ability to diagnose and evaluate available alternatives and opt for the alternatives that appears more suitable and feasible, but when faced with bottlenecks they become disoriented and discouraged to deliver efficiently and effectively on their jobs. As revealed by the theory of constraint, used in the study, constraints create gaps that are inimical and detrimental to the growth and development of an organization including the civil service. Finally, in evaluating the effect of administrative bottlenecks, the study emphasized that the structure through which activities are operationalized should be devoid of bottlenecks that hinders objectives, as the task of organizations are delegating, authority, span of control and work division, among others.

10 | RECOMMENDATIONS

- The study recommends as follows:
- Bureaucracy which is associated with red-tape should be properly managed to enhance efficiency and avoid rigidity and inefficiency, that can lead to administrative bottlenecks in an organization.
- Organizations should avoid too many rules and regulations that alienate and prevent a system from achieving set goals in the practice of public administration.
- New ideas or solutions should be developed to aid the avoidance of administrative bottlenecks in the practice of public administration.
- Streamlining processes, effective communication and leveraging technology should be encouraged to address administrative bottlenecks in the practice of public administration.
- There is need to promote the well-being of workers through ethic training and clear codes of conducts, which are critical in guiding workers behaviour and decision making.

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